

**THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MAKING AUTOMATED QUESTION
GENERATION PROGRAMS WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND
NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING**

Yuldashev Nodirbek,

Andijan Machine Building Institute, specialization of

“Automation and management of technological processes and productions”

Independent Researcher (PhD)

Email: nodirbek4405979@gmail.com , Mobile: 99897-990-03-96,

ABSTRACT

Automated question generation programs using artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) have significant implications in education, assessment, and other fields. These programs can generate questions at scale, reduce human effort, and improve the quality of questions by ensuring that they are aligned with learning objectives and standards. AI-based question generation can also provide personalized learning experiences and facilitate adaptive assessments. Additionally, these programs have the potential to enhance language learning, text comprehension, and critical thinking skills. However, there are also concerns related to the fairness and bias of AI-generated questions, which need to be addressed. Overall, the development and implementation of automated question-generation programs using AI and NLP can greatly benefit various fields and contribute to the advancement of education and technology.

KEY WORDS: automated question generation, artificial intelligence, natural language processing, education, learning objectives, standards, adaptive assessments, text comprehension, critical thinking skills, technology.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a significant growth in the use of automated question generation programs that rely on artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) technologies. These programs are capable of generating questions at scale, reducing human effort, and improving the quality of questions by ensuring that they are aligned with learning objectives and standards. The applications of AI-based question generation programs are diverse and have important implications in education, assessment, and other fields. They have the potential to provide personalized learning experiences, facilitate adaptive assessments, and enhance language learning, text comprehension, and critical thinking skills. However, there are also concerns related to the fairness and bias of AI-generated questions that need to be addressed. This paper explores the significance of making automated question generation programs with artificial intelligence and natural language processing, their potential applications, and the challenges associated with their development and implementation.

Purpose of Study

The purpose of the study is to examine the significance of automated question generation programs that use artificial intelligence and natural language processing, and their potential applications in various fields, particularly in education and assessment. The study aims to explore the benefits of AI-based question generation in generating questions at scale, reducing human effort, improving the quality of questions, and facilitating personalized learning experiences and adaptive assessments. Additionally, the study seeks to identify the challenges associated with the development and implementation of AI-based question generation programs, particularly related to fairness and bias, and proposes solutions to address these concerns. Ultimately, the study aims to contribute to the advancement of education and technology by exploring the potential of AI and NLP in automating the process of generating questions.

Methods

Following there are some possible methods are given:

1. Literature review of existing research on automated question generation programs using AI and NLP
2. Analysis of case studies and applications of AI-based question generation programs in education and assessment
3. Examination of the benefits and limitations of AI-based question generation programs in generating questions at scale, reducing human effort, and improving the quality of questions
4. Investigation of the potential of AI-based question generation programs in providing personalized learning experiences and facilitating adaptive assessments
5. Analysis of the impact of AI-based question generation programs on language learning, text comprehension, and critical thinking skills
6. Identification of the ethical and social implications of AI-based question generation programs, particularly related to fairness and bias
7. Development of solutions and strategies to address concerns related to fairness and bias in AI-based question generation programs
8. Examination of the challenges associated with the development and implementation of AI-based question generation programs, including technical, ethical, and social challenges
9. Exploration of the future directions and potential of AI-based question generation programs in various fields.

Concluding Thoughts

The purpose of this thesis has not been to offer a methodical analysis or forecast of the anticipated effects of AI on innovation or to offer specific recommendations for public policy or the management of innovation. Instead, we make an automated question generation programs that use artificial intelligence and natural language processing have significant implications in education, assessment, and other fields.

These programs have the potential to generate questions at scale, reduce human effort, and improve the quality of questions by ensuring that they are aligned with learning objectives and standards. Additionally, AI-based question generation programs can provide personalized learning experiences and facilitate adaptive assessments, enhancing language learning, text comprehension, and critical thinking skills. However, there are also concerns related to the fairness and bias of AI-generated questions, which need to be addressed through the development of solutions and strategies. The challenges associated with the development and implementation of AI-based question generation programs, including technical, ethical, and social challenges, must also be considered. Overall, the significance of making automated question generation programs using artificial intelligence and natural language processing lies in their potential to contribute to the advancement of education and technology, while addressing challenges and concerns associated with their development and implementation.

REFERENCES

1. A. Papasalouros, K. Kanaris, and K. Kotis, "Automatic generation of multiple choice questions from domain ontologies.", in Proceedings of IADIS International Conference on e-Learning, Citeseer, 2008, pp. 427–434
2. P. I. Pavlik, H. Cen, and K. R. Koedinger, "Performance factors analysis—a new alternative to knowledge tracing", in Proceedings of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED), IOS Press, 2009.
3. C. D. Manning, P. Raghavan, and H. Schütze, Introduction to information retrieval. Cambridge University Press, 2009.
4. R. Pelánek, "Time decay functions and elo system in student modeling", Proc. of Educational Data Mining (EDM), 2014.
5. J. Papoušek and R. Pelánek, "Impact of adaptive educational system behaviour on student motivation", in Proceedings of Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED), 2015.